

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Saparova Qunduz Otaboevna

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF SIMPLE SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK (IN THE EXAMPLE
OF SOCIAL NETWORKS)

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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2023-2024

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ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX